

EXPERIMENTAL PACKAGE - ADoTe (instruments in English)

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1. Initial considerations

This document is supplementary material to the article “*ADoTe: Approach to teaching and learning functional testing technique criteria supported by Testing Dojo*”. It presents the objects, guidelines, and measurement instruments used in the executions of the controlled experiment conducted to evaluate ADoTe.

The instruments presented in the following sections were translated to English. If necessary, the reader can find their original descriptions (in Brazilian Portuguese) in the file “expPackage_pt.pdf”.

2. Treatments and materials/objects used for teaching and learning

This section describes the treatments and materials/objects used for teaching and learning (based on the second execution of the experiment; the differences regarding the first execution are exposed in the article).

Subsections 2.a and 2.b detail the instance of ADoTe (experimental group treatment) and the traditional teaching approach (control group treatment) used in the experiment, respectively. The approaches have two parts: one with a theoretical focus (the same for both) and another with a practical focus (distinct between them). The descriptions below are organized concerning such parts. Finally, subsection 2.c exposes a set of slides made available to the participants as a supporting material and also used in a video presented in the first part of the approaches.

2.a. Instance of ADoTe (experimental group treatment)

First part (moment with a theoretical focus - M1)

This moment included the reproduction of a video (projected in the room) about functional testing technique criteria (the video explained the slides presented in subsection 2.c) followed by thirty minutes in which students could discuss and question the researchers about its content.

Second part (moment with a practical focus - M2)

This moment (of 110 minutes) was supported by:

- The set of slides (see section 2.c) used in the video reproduced in the first part of the approach. This material was made available in a Moodle environment at the beginning of the activity, so that participants could use it while solving the practical exercises.
- An online form (its content will be presented in this section) with dojo missions. The form was made available in a Moodle environment at the beginning of the activity, was only accessible by the experimental group, and was used during the execution of the activities.
- A dynamic online presentation (its content will be presented in this section) with explanations about testing dojos and resources that allowed participants to share their responses to the missions.
- A development environment composed of: (a) Eclipse Java EE IDE version Oxygen.3a Release (4.7.3a); (b) JUnit 5 framework; and (c) a Java project. The environment was set up on the researcher's computer, which was used by the participants in the fourth mission.
- A retrospective questionnaire (see section 5).

The teaching and learning moment (*M2*) was composed of the six macro-activities below, which were defined based on the typical structure of a dojo:

1. (7 min) Dojo introduction: at this moment the concept of testing dojo was presented to the participants with the support of some slides from the dynamic online presentation.
2. (3 min) Initial agreements: included the presentation of the activities planned to be executed in the dojo and their objectives.
3. (15 min) Execution — Resolution of a mission using the Prepared Kata format. The mission form and slides from the dynamic online presentation were used as supporting materials.
4. (45 min) Execution — Resolution of two missions using the Kake format. The mission form and slides from the dynamic online presentation were used as supporting materials.
5. (30 min) Execution — Resolution of a mission using the Randori/Paired Session format. The mission form, slides from the dynamic online presentation, and the development environment specified above were used as supporting materials.

6. (10 min) Retrospective: at this moment, participants filled out the retrospective questionnaire.

The six macro-activities will be detailed below.

1. Dojo introduction

First, the researcher announced to the participants that the teaching-learning moment would occur through a testing dojo and presented its concept with the support of the slide below.

Testing Dojo - Concepts AhaSlides

- Dojo: in the context of martial arts it refers to a training place
- **Testing dojo:**
 - Environment/dynamics/moment of practice and learning of testing content. In a dojo, missions (also called katas, challenges, etc.) on the subject are solved collaboratively. Each execution of a dojo is called a session
 - **Fun** and safe moment (no pressure; **mistakes are acceptable**) where participants can test new ideas and learn continuously, in a **collaborative** (non-competitive) and inclusive way. Missions are usually solved in **small steps** ("baby steps") so that everyone can understand them
- **Structure**
 - *Dojo introduction:* concept, goals, structure, rules, expected personal behaviors and attitudes
 - *Initial agreements:* what will be accomplished
 - *Execution:* resolution of the mission
 - *Retrospective:* reflection and sharing of opinions about the session
- **Roles:**
 - Facilitator
 - Tester/pilot
 - Recorder/copilot
 - Observers

Next, the researcher presented the dojo formats known as Prepared Kata and Kake by explaining the content of the following slide.

Testing Dojo - Formats AhaSlides

- **Prepared Kata:**
 - The **facilitator** presents the step-by-step process for solving the mission
 - **Observers** can ask questions
- **Kake:**
 - **Multiple pairs** work simultaneously on the same mission on different computers (one per pair)
 - The **tester/pilot** is the only one who can use the keyboard and mouse. He is responsible for the execution of the mission and must discuss the actions to be taken with the recorder
 - The **register/copilot** provides support to the tester through suggestions/ideas and notes of what is being done
 - The pair works on the mission for a **time set** (5-7 min). After this time, the **pairs are changed:** the participants who played the role of pilot become copilots in another pair; those who acted as copilots remain on the same computer, but now as pilots; new pairs must be formed in each round

After the explanations, the initial agreements were established.

2. Initial agreements

First, the researcher asked the participants to organize themselves into pairs (using a single computer per pair) and access the mission form and the slides from section 2.c.

Next, projecting the computer screen into the environment, the researcher opened the mission form and read aloud the content of its first section (shown in the image below), explaining to the participants how the dojo would be conducted and what would be accomplished.

Testing Dojo
Functional Testing
Technique Criteria

Missions/Katas

Consider that you are part of the team responsible for testing the software to be used for the launch and control of a space probe.

The following missions will present specifications of some of the functionalities of this software. Your task will be to test them using **functional testing technique criteria**.

In the first mission we will use the **Prepared Kata** format and in the second and third the **Kata** format. In these missions we will practice:

- Test case design (focusing on functional testing technique criteria)
- Test execution
- Test report/documentation

For the fourth and final mission, we will use the **paired session/Randori** format and we will also practice:

- Test automation

Are you ready? At the dojo facilitator's command, click "Next".

[Next](#) [Clear form](#)

Once the explanations were finished, the researcher asked the participants to access the next section of the form, doing the same.

3. Execution — Resolution of a mission using the Prepared Kata format

This moment included the presentation of the step-by-step resolution of the mission (prepared by the researcher) to the participants, who were allowed to ask questions if they

had any doubts (dynamics of the Prepared Kata format). The information presented in the images below was used as a supporting resource.

Mission 1

Considering the **equivalence partitioning** criterion, you should:

1. Read the specification below and define the appropriate equivalence classes
2. Create the necessary test cases (minimum set) to cover the classes/meet the criteria requested
3. Run the program using the test cases created and check whether the outputs obtained are the same as expected (success) or not (failure). To do this, for each test case you must enter the test data in the field provided for this purpose and then click outside of it to obtain the output
4. Record the results of the testing activity at <https://ahaslides.com/DOJOT> in the following format:

Classes:

Identifier of class 1: description of class 1 (valid - V or invalid - I)

Identifier of class n: description of class n (valid - V or invalid - I)

Criterion name

Class identifier: test cases separated by semicolons and in the format

(test data, expected output): obtained output (success - S or failure - F)

Example for the condition "input must be greater than 0":

Classes:

C1: input > 0 (V)

C2: input <= 0 (I)

Boundary value analysis:

C1: (1, input accepted): input accepted (S);

C2: (-1, input refused): input refused (S); (0, input refused): input accepted (F)

Context: consider that among the system's functionalities there is a command terminal.

Specification: when attempting to be executed, commands containing the characters \$ or % must be ignored. In these cases, the message "Command ignored" must be displayed.

Tip: a specification can be formed by multiple conditions. In these cases, try to analyze the conditions separately.

Test data:

Enter the commands (one at a time) in the field below and then click outside of it. If no message is displayed, it means the command was accepted.

Your answer

Wait for the dojo facilitator's guidance to click "Next".

Back

Next

Clear form

Guideline: if the input condition is **boolean** (specify a “must-be” situation), a valid and an invalid class must be defined

Classes:

C1: command does not have \$ (V)

C3: command does not have % (V)

C2: command has \$ (I)

C4: command has % (I)

Equivalence partitioning:

C1 and C3: (any input without \$ and %, command should not be ignored)

C2: (any input with \$, but without %, "Command ignored")

C4: (any input with %, but without \$, "Command ignored")

Once the activities regarding the first mission were finished, the researcher asked the participants to access the next section of the form, doing the same.

4. Execution — Resolution of two missions using the Kake format

The dynamics followed to solve missions two and three were:

1. Participants had a few minutes (seven for mission 2, eight for the first part of mission 3 and three for the second part of mission 3) to solve a mission or part of it in pairs. As supporting resources, they were allowed to use the slides from section 2.c, the internet, and ask the researcher about the process. The mission form was used to read the instructions and descriptions of the missions, as well as execute the tests. Participants answered the missions on slides from the dynamic online presentation (more details below).
2. After the time allocated to solving a mission or part of it (hereinafter called a step), the researcher (playing the role of facilitator) presented the answers submitted by peers to all participants and promoted a discussion about them and the possible/correct answers for the mission.
3. Finally, the facilitator organized the rotation of pairs (following the rules of the Kake format, explained in the introductory slide) and asked the participants to start the next mission or step.

Considering the dynamics above, first the researcher explained to the participants how they should proceed regarding the second mission. Then, participants worked on the mission (its description can be seen in the image below) during the time allocated for it.

Mission 2

Considering the **equivalence partitioning** criterion, you should:

1. Read the specification below and define the appropriate equivalence classes
2. Create the necessary test cases (minimum set) to cover the classes/meet the criteria requested
3. Run the program using the test cases created and check whether the outputs obtained are the same as expected (success) or not (failure). To do this, for each test case you must enter the test data in the field provided for this purpose and then click outside of it to obtain the output
4. Record the results of the testing activity at <https://ahaslides.com/DOJOT> in the following format:

Classes:

Identifier of class 1: description of class 1 (valid - V or invalid - I)

Identifier of class n: description of class n (valid - V or invalid - I)

Criterion name

Class identifier: test cases separated by semicolons and in the format

(test data, expected output): obtained output (success - S or failure - F)

Example for the condition "input must be greater than 0":

Classes:

C1: $input > 0$ (V)

C2: $input \leq 0$ (I)

Boundary value analysis:

C1: (1, input accepted): input accepted (S);

C2: (-1, input refused): input refused (S); (0, input refused): input accepted (F)

Context: consider that the probe has four thrusters – identified by the letters L (east), O (west), N (north) and S (south) – and a functionality responsible for activating them.

Specification: it must be possible to define (in a text field) which thruster must be activated to move the probe (only one at a time): L, O, N, or S.

Test data:

To test the thruster activation functionality, enter data in the field below and then click outside the field. If no error message is displayed, consider that the thruster has been activated.

Your answer _____

Now consider that, instead of using a text input field, the thruster to be activated was defined using a component like the one shown below (dropdown).

Would there be any difference regarding the test cases?

Answer with "Yes" or "No".

Choose ▼

Wait for the dojo facilitator's guidance to click "Next".

Back

Next

Clear form

Responses were submitted by participants on a page/slide of the dynamic online presentation (see the next image). To facilitate the discussion, participants were asked to also inform the peer identifier (a letter associated with the computer they were using).

After the time allocated for solving the mission, the researcher shared a screen like the one shown below, on which the answers from all pairs were displayed (while solving the mission, the pairs were unable to see each other's answers). Based on the answers provided by peers, a discussion on the resolution of the mission was then mediated.

It is noteworthy that the answers and explanations presented by the researcher to the experimental group were analogous to those that participants in the control group received. The answer presented for the second mission can be seen in the image below.

Guideline: if the input condition specifies a **set of values** and the program could handle them differently, a valid class must be defined for each value of the set and an invalid class must be defined for another value

Classes:

C1: input = L (V)

C2: input = O (V)

C3: input = N (V)

C4: input = S (V)

C5: input != L, O, N or S (I)

Equivalence partitioning:

C1: (L, thruster L is activated)

C2: (O, thruster O is activated)

C3: (N, thruster N is activated)

C4: (S, thruster S is activated)

C5: (any input != L, O, N or S, no thruster is activated)

Some components (e.g., dropdown) may limit the test of the invalid class (C5)

After discussing the content of the slide above, a pair rotation was conducted and the resolution of the third mission began (using the same dynamics as the second). This mission was divided into two parts (see the image below), with a pair rotation before starting step two.

Mission 3

First Step

Considering the **equivalence partitioning** and the **boundary value analysis** criteria, you should:

1. Read the specification below and define the appropriate equivalence classes
2. Create the necessary test cases (minimum set) to cover the classes/meet the criteria requested
3. Run the program using the test cases created and check whether the outputs obtained are the same as expected (success) or not (failure). To do this, for each test case you must enter the test data in the field provided for this purpose and then click outside of it to obtain the output
4. Record the results of the testing activity at <https://ahaslides.com/DOJOT> in the following format:

Classes:

Identifier of class 1: description of class 1 (valid - V or invalid - I)

Identifier of class n: description of class n (valid - V or invalid - I)

Criterion name

Class identifier: test cases separated by semicolons and in the format

(test data, expected output): obtained output (success - S or failure - F)

Example for the condition "input must be greater than 0":

Classes:

C1: *input > 0 (V)*

C2: *input <= 0 (I)*

Boundary value analysis:

C1: *(1, input accepted): input accepted (S);*

C2: *(-1, input refused): input refused (S); (0, input refused): input accepted (F)*

```
0111001011
1101010110001001
0101110101011111
0101010101011100
100001010101
```

Context: consider that the probe sends information to Earth through blocks of characters. The characters in the first line of a block are used to verify the integrity of the information that follows. The system has a feature that validates the data of this line.

Specification: the number of characters in the first line of an incorrupt block is equal to 10. If a different number of characters is displayed, the message "Invalid block" must be displayed.

Test data:

Enter the first line of the character block in the field below and then click outside the field. If no error message is displayed, consider that the line was considered valid.

Your answer

Second Step

Answer (at <https://ahaslides.com/DOJOT>) with "Yes" or "No" each question below:

1. Considering the specification of this mission, is it possible to create a minimal set of test cases that meets the **equivalence partitioning** criterion but does not meet the **boundary value analysis** criterion?
2. Considering the specification of this mission, is it possible to create a minimum set of test cases that meets the **boundary value analysis** criterion but does not meet the **equivalence partitioning** criterion?
3. The **systematic functional testing** criterion provides guidelines for testing different values and text/string data. Would such guidelines support the identification of potential failures in the functionality of this mission that might not be noticed in the test cases created using the previous criteria?

Wait for the dojo facilitator's guidance to click "Next".

Back
Next

Clear form

The submission and response pages (used by the participants) were analogous to those of mission 2. The slides with the researcher's answers are presented below.

Mission 3 - Answer (First Step)

Guideline: if the input condition specifies a **number of values** or requires a **specific value**, one valid class and two invalid classes must be defined

Classes:

- C1: 1st line with 10c (V)
- C2: 1st line with less than 10c (I)
- C3: 1st line with more than 10c (I)

Equivalence partitioning:

- C1: (input with 10c, valid block)
- C2: (input with less than 10c, "Invalid block")
- C3: (input with more than 10c, "Invalid block")

Boundary value analysis:

- C1: (input with 10c, valid block)
- C2: (input with 9c, "Invalid block")
- C3: (input with 11c, "Invalid block")

Mission 3 - Answer (Second Step)

Equivalence partitioning:

C2: (input with less than 10c, "Invalid block")

C3: (input with more than 10c, "Invalid block")

Boundary value analysis:

C2: (input with 9c, "Invalid block")

C3: (input with 11c, "Invalid block")

1. Is it possible to satisfy **equivalence partitioning** but not **boundary value analysis**? A.: Yes

E.g.: input with less than 9c to C2 or input with more than 11c to C3

2. Is it possible to satisfy **boundary value analysis** but not **equivalence partitioning**? A.: No

3. Would **systematic functional testing** guidelines support failure identification...? A.: Yes

E.g.: inputs of size 0, inputs of huge size, with special characters, spaces (should spaces be considered valid?). Which characters should be considered valid? Only ASCII?

The discussion of the content of the slide above concluded the activities in the Kake format, which was followed by the actions described in the next section.

5. Execution — Resolution of a mission using the Randori/Paired Session format

In the fourth mission, the Randori/Paired Session format was used. Initially, the researcher conceptualized this format to the participants using the slide below.

Testing Dojo - Formats

- Paired session/Randori:
 - Only **one pair** works at a time, sharing a computer whose **screen is projected in the room**
 - The **tester/pilot** is the only one who can use the keyboard and mouse. He is responsible for the execution of the mission. The **recorder/copilot** supports the tester through suggestions/ideas and notes
 - Tester and recorder should **discuss the actions out loud** so that observers can understand the actions being taken and their motivation. The pair can involve observers **when they are unsure of what to do**
 - **Observers** must pay attention to what is being done and may speak up when the pair asks for support
 - The pair works on the mission for a **time set** (a few minutes). After this time, the **pair is changed**: the participant who played the role of copilot becomes the pilot; the one who acted as pilot returns to the observer group; a member of the observer group becomes copilot; new pairs must be formed for each round

Next, with the support of the last section of the mission form, the facilitator presented the mission to the participants and explained to them how it should be solved.

Mission 4

In the fourth and final mission we will use the testing dojo format known as a **paired session/Randori**.

Functional tests can be performed not only manually, but also in an automated manner. Automation is interesting because it allows, for example, tests to be run several times in a more agile (allowing quick and constant feedback) and safer manner (manual tests are prone to human error).

For the automation of unit tests (and considering projects in the Java language), the JUnit framework can be used, for example. In its version 5, a test method (which can be understood as corresponding to a test case) is defined as follows:

```
@Test                // Annotation indicating that the method is a testing method
public void testCase_nn() { // Method signature
    Method body
}
```

In the "method body" variables can be defined, methods can be called, etc. The JUnit 5 *Assertions* class has methods that make testing easier and can be used in this part of the code. Examples include:

- **assertEquals(expected_output, obtained_output)**: compares the expected_output with the obtained_output. Results in success if both are equal and in failure if they are different;
- **assertTrue(boolean_condition)**: results in success if boolean_condition is true. Otherwise, it results in failure;
- **assertFalse(boolean_condition)**: results in success if boolean_condition is false. Otherwise, it results in failure.

Knowing this, in this mission we will automate unit tests with the support of the JUnit 5 framework (in the Eclipse IDE), exercising, at the same time, the **equivalence partitioning**, **boundary value analysis** and **systematic functional testing** criteria for the specification below.

Context: consider that the probe performs calculations and sends the results to a robot that is landed on Mars. This robot stores the received values in a field with a bit limit (32 bits using the sign-magnitude representation, i.e., it can store values from -2147483647 to 2147483647). Given this limitation, a system functionality was developed to receive the results of various calculations from the probe and validate them before sending them to the robot.

Specification: a value must be accepted for sending to the robot if it is between -2147483647 and 2147483647, inclusive. The functionality must return whether the value is valid (true) or not (false).

Method signature: public boolean checkOutput(String s)

Class: Probe (as the tests are functional, the implementation of the class will not be presented)

This mission will be solved on a single computer (whose screen is being projected in the environment) through baby steps. Thus, in each round only one of the following items will be acted upon, respecting the order presented (an item will be analyzed only if the previous ones have already been met).

Equivalence partitioning:

- *If there are still equivalence classes to be defined:* define a new equivalence class, implement a test case for it, run the test and check the output
- *If the equivalence partitioning criterion is already fully met:* report this to the rest of the dojo and move on to the next criterion

Boundary value analysis:

- *If in the test set there is a test case that does not meet the boundary value analysis criterion:* replace this test case (only one) with another that meets the boundary value analysis criterion and corresponds to the same equivalence class as the removed one; run the test and check the output
- *If all test cases in the suite are valid regarding to the boundary value analysis criterion:*
 - *If the boundary value analysis criterion is still not completely met:* implement a test case missing for the criterion, run the test and check the output
 - *If the boundary value analysis criterion is already fully met:* report this to the rest of the dojo and move on to the next criterion

Systematic functional testing:

- *If the systematic functional testing criterion is not yet fully met:* tell the dojo which guideline/situation still needs to be covered/tested, implement a test case for it, run the test and check the output
- *If the systematic functional testing criterion is already fully met:* report this to the rest of the dojo

At the end of the mission this page can be closed (it is not necessary to click "Submit").

Back

Submit

Clear form

The dynamics followed to solve the fourth mission were:

1. The mission was solved on a single computer (on the researcher's machine, whose screen was projected into the environment) through small steps (called baby steps). The items on the form were solved by just one pair per time (composed of one participant acting as a tester/pilot and another acting as a recorder). The pair had up to two minutes to act on the item. While the pair was solving the mission, the other participants acted as observers.
2. Once the the time allocated for the pair had finished, the researcher (acting as the facilitator) commented on the pair's solution, making, if necessary, additional explanations or adjustments in understanding.
3. If there was still time available and outstanding items to complete the mission (which could be solved in nine to twelve steps, depending on the answers provided by the participants), the facilitator organized the pair rotation following the rules of the format. Then, the new pair started solving another step/item of the mission. In turn, if the mission had been completely solved or the time limit for the moment had been reached, the researcher organized the end of the session, reviewing out loud the solution developed by the participants or presenting them with the missing part, respectively.

The image below presents the IDE and project/code made available to participants in the beginning of the mission.

```

1 @/**
2  * Métodos:
3  * assertEquals(resultado_esperado, resultado_obtido, mensagem_opcional_erro)
4  * assertTrue(condicao_booleana, mensagem_opcional_erro)
5  * assertFalse(condicao_booleana, mensagem_opcional_erro)
6  */
7
8 package br.sonda.tests;
9
10 import br.sonda.code.*;
11 import static org.junit.jupiter.api.Assertions.*;
12 import org.junit.jupiter.api.BeforeEach;
13 import org.junit.jupiter.api.Test;
14
15 class Tests {
16
17     public Sonda sd;
18
19     @BeforeEach
20     public void inicializar() {
21         sd = new Sonda();
22     }
23
24     // Início da definição dos casos de teste:
25     @Test
26     public void casoTeste_01() {
27         boolean resultadoObtido = sd.validarResultado("0");
28         assertEquals(true, resultadoObtido);
29     }
30
31     // Insira os demais casos de testes aqui
32
33 }
34

```

The slide used to present the mission answer is exposed below.

Mission 4 - Answer

Guideline: if the input condition specifies a **range of values**, one valid and two invalid classes must be defined

Equivalence partitioning |

Boundary value analysis:

- (-2147483648, false)
- (-2147483647, true)
- (-2147483646, true)
- (2147483646, true)
- (2147483647, true)
- (2147483648, false)

Systematic functional testing (additionally):

- (input less than -2147483648, false)
- (input greater than 2147483648, false)
- (0, true)
- (space, false)
- (input of size 0, false)
- (input of a huge size, false)
- (input with alphabetic/special characters, false)
- (input in real number format, false)

The next section presents the last moment of the approach.

6. Retrospective

In the last ten minutes, the retrospective questionnaire was made available in the Moodle environment and participants were instructed to fill it out. Submission of the answered questionnaire ended the activities of the approach.

2.b. Traditional teaching approach (control group treatment)

First part (moment with a theoretical focus)

This moment included the reproduction of a video (projected in the room) about functional testing technique criteria (the video explained the slides presented in subsection 2.c) followed by thirty minutes in which students could discuss and question the researchers about its content.

Second part (moment with a practical focus)

This moment (of 110 minutes) was supported by:

- The set of slides (see section 2.c) used in the video reproduced in the first part of the approach. This material was made available in a Moodle environment at the beginning of the activity, so that participants could use it while solving the practical exercises.
- A document (its content will be presented in this section) containing the exercises to be solved by the participants. The document was made available in a Moodle environment at the beginning of the activity and was only accessible by the control group.
- A document containing the answers to the exercises (its content will be presented in this section). The document was made available in a Moodle environment sixty minutes after the participants began solving the exercises and was only accessible by the control group.
- A retrospective questionnaire (see section 5).

The teaching and learning moment was composed of the three macro-activities below:

1. (60 min) Resolution of the exercises by the participants.
2. (40 min) Correction of the exercises by the participants.
3. (10 min) Retrospective.

The three macro-activities will be detailed below.

1. Resolution of the exercises by the participants

First, the document with the exercises was made available in the Moodle environment (its content can be seen in the images below). Then, the researcher asked participants to access the document and follow its instructions.

EXERCISE LIST

Instructions:

- In this document you will find exercises/questions about functional testing technique criteria. Your task in this activity is to answer them.
- While solving the exercises, you can use the slides available on Moodle, as well as conduct research on the internet. However, you should not talk to other study participants.
- You should record your answers in the media/application of your choice (e.g., a text editor, paper, etc.). Your answers will not need to be sent to the researchers (they will be used by you in the next activity of the study).
- The time to complete the activity will be 60 minutes. During this time, you may ask the researcher accompanying your group if you have any questions about the process being adopted in the activity, but not about the answers to the exercises and/or content related to functional testing technique criteria.

Exercises:

Initial notes: when solving the exercises, consider that you are part of the team responsible for testing the software to be used for the launch and control of a space probe.

In exercises **1**, **2.1**, and **3.1**, write the equivalence classes and test cases in the following format:

Classes:
Identifier of class 1: description of class 1 (valid - V or invalid - I)
Identifier of class n: description of class n (valid - V or invalid - I)

Criterion name (repeat this block for each criterion requested in the question)
Class identifier: test cases separated by semicolons and in the format
(test data, expected output)

Example for the condition "input must be greater than 0" and the boundary value analysis criterion:

Classes:
C1: *input > 0 (V)*
C2: *input <= 0 (I)*

Boundary value analysis:
C1: *(1, input accepted)*
C2: *(-1, input refused); (0, input refused)*

Question 1:

Considering the **equivalence partitioning** criterion: read the specification below and define the appropriate equivalence classes; create the necessary test cases (minimum set) to cover the classes/meet the criterion requested.

Context: consider that among the system's functionalities there is a command terminal.

Specification: when attempting to be executed, commands containing the characters \$ or % must be ignored. In these cases, the message "Command ignored" must be displayed.

Tip: a specification can be formed by multiple conditions. In these cases, try to analyze the conditions separately.

Question 2:

2.1. Considering the **equivalence partitioning** criterion: read the specification below and define the appropriate equivalence classes; create the necessary test cases (minimum set) to cover the classes/meet the criterion requested.

Context: consider that the probe has four thrusters — identified by the letters L (east), O (west), N (north) and S (south) — and a functionality responsible for activating them.

Specification: it must be possible to define (in a text field) which thruster must be activated to move the probe (only one at a time): L, O, N, or S.

2.2. Now consider that, instead of using a text input field, the thruster to be activated was defined using a component like the one shown below (dropdown).

Choose ▾
Choose
L
O
N
S

Would there be any difference regarding the test cases?

Question 3:

3.1. Considering the **equivalence partitioning** and the **boundary value analysis** criteria: read the specification below and define the appropriate equivalence classes; create the necessary test cases (minimum set) to cover the classes/meet the criteria requested.

Context: consider that the probe sends information to Earth through blocks of characters. The characters in the first line of a block are used to verify the integrity of the information that follows. The system has a feature that validates the data of this line.

Specification: the number of characters in the first line of an incorrupt block is equal to 10. If a different number of characters is displayed, the message "Invalid block" must be displayed.

3.2. Considering the specification presented in question 3.1, is it possible to create a minimum set of test cases that meets the **equivalence partitioning** criterion but does not meet the **boundary value analysis** criterion?

3.3. Considering the specification presented in question 3.1, is it possible to create a minimum set of test cases that meets the **boundary value analysis** criterion but does not meet the **equivalence partitioning** criterion?

3.4. The **systematic functional testing** criterion provides guidelines for testing different values and text/string data. Would such guidelines support the identification of potential failures in the functionality of question 3.1 that might not be noticed in the test cases created using the previous criteria?

Question 4:

Functional tests can be performed not only manually, but also in an automated manner. Automation is interesting because it allows, for example, tests to be run several times in a more agile (allowing quick and constant feedback) and safer manner (manual tests are prone to human error). For the automation of unit tests (and considering projects in the Java language), the JUnit framework can be used, for example. In its version 5, a test method (which can be understood as corresponding to a test case) is defined as follows:

```
@Test // Annotation indicating that the method is a testing method
public void testCase_nn() { // Method signature
    Method body
}
```

In the "method body" variables can be defined, methods can be called, etc. The JUnit 5 *Assertions* class has methods that make testing easier and can be used in this part of the code. Examples include:

- `assertEquals(expected_output, obtained_output)`: compares the `expected_output` with the `obtained_output`. Results in success if both are equal and failure if they are different.
- `assertTrue(boolean_condition)`: results in success if `boolean_condition` is true. Otherwise, it results in failure.
- `assertFalse(boolean_condition)`: results in success if `boolean_condition` is false. Otherwise, it results in failure.

Considering the descriptions above, create automated test cases using at least one of the JUnit 5 methods mentioned (`assertEquals`, `assertTrue` ou `assertFalse`). The test cases must be created regarding the following specification and meet the **equivalence partitioning**, **boundary value analysis**, and **systematic functional testing** criteria.

Context: consider that the probe performs calculations and sends the results to a robot that is landed on Mars. This robot stores the received values in a field with a bit limit (32 bits using the sign-magnitude representation, i.e., it can store values from -2147483647 to 2147483647). Given this limitation, a system functionality was developed to receive the results of various calculations from the probe and validate them before sending them to the robot.

Specification: a value must be accepted for sending to the robot if it is between -2147483647 and 2147483647, inclusive. The functionality must return whether the value is valid (true) or not (false).

Method signature: `public boolean checkOutput(String s)`

Class: `Probe` (as the tests are functional, the implementation of the class will not be presented)

```
1 package br.probe.tests;
2
3 import br.probe.code.*;
4 import static org.junit.jupiter.api.Assertions.*;
5 import org.junit.jupiter.api.BeforeEach;
6 import org.junit.jupiter.api.Test;
7
8 class Tests {
9     public Probe pb;
10
11     @BeforeEach
12     public void init() {
13         pb = new Probe();
14     }
15
16     // Test case example
17     @Test
18     public void testCase_01() {
19         boolean obtainedOutput = pb.checkOutput("0");
20         assertEquals(true, obtainedOutput);
21     }
22
23     // Add the other test cases here
24 }
```

Above is the code where your tests would be included (line 23). In the block preceding the comment, an example of a test case that uses the `assertEquals` method is presented. The `checkOutput()` method corresponds to the functionality mentioned in the specification. In the example, the value `0` is being used as test data, and the output obtained from running the program with this test data is stored in the variable `obtainedOutput`. This variable is used in the `assertEquals` method to compare the obtained output with the expected output (`true`). When running the test, if the outputs are the same JUnit 5 will indicate success for the test case. Otherwise, it will indicate a failure.

Note: in this exercise, you just need to write the methods (related to the test cases) that you would add to the code above.

2. Correction of the exercises by the participants

After the time planned for the moment described in the previous section, a document containing the answers to the exercises was made available in the Moodle

environment (its content can be seen in the images below). Participants were then instructed to compare their answers to the resolutions provided in the document. During this activity, they were also allowed to ask questions to the researcher about the exercises.

ANSWER PATTERNS

Instructions:

- This document describes the expected answer patterns for the exercises/questions you have just answered.
- You must individually compare your answers to those presented in this document, checking whether your answers are correct and complete, as well as understanding which are the appropriate solutions to the exercises.
- If you have any questions about the answers presented in this document, you can ask the researcher who accompanies your group.
- The time to complete this activity will be 40 minutes from the moment this document is made available.

Answers:

Question 1:

Classes:

C1: command does not have \$ (V)

C3: command does not have % (V)

C2: command has the character \$ (I)

C4: command has the character % (I)

Equivalence partitioning:

C1 and C3: (any input without the characters \$ and %, command should not be ignored)

C2: (any input with the character \$, but without the character %, "Command ignored")

C4: (any input with the character %, but without the character \$, "Command ignored")

Notes:

- The specification presents multiple conditions due to the use of the "or" operator in the description of the determined set of characters that cannot exist in the command. Thus, the conditions were analyzed separately and appropriate classes were created for each of them.
- Each of the test data for C2 and C4 must contain only one of the characters that cannot exist in commands (\$ or %), since invalid classes must be covered/tested in an exclusive manner. This is necessary because: imagine that the functionality presents a fault/defect, refusing commands with the \$ character, but not doing the same for commands with the % character. Creating a single test case with both characters (or only with \$) would not reveal the defect, since the command of this test case would be ignored due to the presence of the \$ character. However, commands with % (but without \$) would not be ignored, which is contrary to the specification.

Question 2:

2.1: the input condition specifies a specific set of values and the program can manipulate them differently. Thus, the answer is:

Classes:

C1: input equal to L (V)

C2: input equal to O (V)

C3: input equal to N (V)

C4: input equal to S (V)

C5: input different from L, O, N, or S (I)

Equivalence partitioning:

C1: (L, thruster L is activated)

C2: (O, thruster O is activated)

C3: (N, thruster N is activated)

C4: (S, thruster S is activated)

C5: (any input different from L, O, N, or S, no thruster is activated)

2.2: the presented component may limit the testing of C5 (it may not be possible to enter invalid test data, since only valid options are listed in the dropdown). However, if the component allows an option to not be selected (staying on "Choose", for example), C5 can be tested with that option, since the program may interpret it as a null input, a valid enumerator value, etc.

Question 3:

3.1: the input condition specifies a number of values/specific value. Thus, the answer is:

Classes:

C1: first line with 10 characters (V)

C2: first line with less than 10 characters (I)

C3: first line with more than 10 characters (I)

Equivalence partitioning:

C1: (input with exactly 10 characters, the block must be consider valid)

C2: (input with less than 10 characters, "Invalid block")

C3: (input with more than 10 characters, "Invalid block")

Boundary value analysis:

C1: (input with exactly 10 characters, the block must be consider valid)

C2: (input with exactly 9 characters, "Invalid block")

C3: (input with exactly 11 characters, "Invalid block")

3.2: Yes. This is possible if the set of test cases created to cover the equivalence partitioning criterion presents (considering the classes from the answer of question 3.1):

- For C2, a test data with less than 9 characters; and/or
- For C3, a test data with more than 11 characters.

3.3: No. The set of test cases created to cover the boundary value analysis criterion is unique and also covers the equivalence partitioning criterion.

3.4: Yes. Test cases with data as those described below could help identify faults/defects: inputs of size 0, with a huge size, with special characters or spaces.

Test cases with special characters and spaces could even help identify gaps in the specification, by raising questions such as: should spaces be considered valid characters for the functionality? Which characters should be considered valid: only those from the ASCII set or those from other character sets as well? These observations also highlight the importance of good specifications for creating test cases for the functional technique.

Question 4:

The test cases (test data, expected result) necessary to cover equivalence partitioning and boundary value analysis criteria are:

- (-2147483648, false)
- (-2147483647, true)
- (-2147483646, true)
- (2147483646, true)
- (2147483647, true)
- (2147483648, false)

Additionally, to cover the systematic functional testing criterion it is necessary to ensure the existence of at least two test cases for each equivalence class. Therefore, it is also necessary:

- (input less than -2147483648, false)
- (input greater than 2147483648, false)

Still considering the systematic functional testing criterion, it is also recommended to create test cases with inputs equal to 0, space, with size 0, with a huge size, with alphabetic/special characters, and in the format of real numbers, for example. The output must be false for all cases (except for the one whose input is the value 0).

Considering the test cases above and the methods of the *Assertions* class mentioned in the question, it is expected that:

- For test cases with an expected output equal to true: that methods `assertEquals` (with `true` in the first parameter) or `assertTrue` have been used.
- For test cases with an expected output equal to false: that methods `assertEquals` (with `false` in the first parameter) or `assertFalse` have been used.
- The outputs have been obtained (regardless of the method used; `assertEquals`, `assertTrue`, or `assertFalse`) through `pb.checkOutput("test_data")`, where `test_data` is replaced by the test data (value).
 - It is worth noting that, in addition to the code form presented in the example (where a variable was used to store the obtained output), `pb.checkOutput("test_data")` can also be informed directly in the second parameter of the method `assertEquals` or as the first parameter in the methods `assertTrue` or `assertFalse`.

3. Retrospective

In the last ten minutes, the retrospective questionnaire was made available in the Moodle environment and participants were instructed to fill it out. Submission of the answered questionnaire ended the activities of the approach.

2.c. Slides about functional testing technique criteria

Instrument content:

Functional Testing Technique Criteria	Software testing: definitions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Software testing: definitions 2 Testing techniques and criteria <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functional technique 3 Functional testing technique criteria <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equivalence partitioning • Boundary value analysis • Systematic functional testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essential activity and also the most widespread for software quality assurance • Dynamic activity → execution of a program or model using specific input data + checking its behavior (whether it matches what is expected) • Objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is not to show that the program is correct (there are theoretical and practical limitations), but reveal the presence of defects/failures if they exist
<p>Typical testing activity scenario: elements</p>	<p>Typical testing activity scenario: elements</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considering a model/program P: 	
<p>Typical testing activity scenario: elements</p>	<p>Typical testing activity scenario: elements</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test data - d: an element of $D(P)$ 	

Typical testing activity scenario: elements

- Test suite or test case set: set of all test cases used during a given testing activity

Typical testing activity scenario: elements

- Oracle: instrument (e.g., tester or automated tool) that decides whether the output obtained from a given execution of P matches the expected output

Typical testing activity scenario: elements

- The oracle may use the program specification ($S(P)$) or another artifact that defines its behavior

Typical testing activity scenario

- Having been defined a set of test cases T from $D(P)$, the program under test P is executed with T and the obtained outputs are verified. The verification of the correctness of an execution is performed by an oracle (O), which uses $S(P)$ or another artifact that defines the behavior of P . If the output of the execution of P matches what was expected, then no error was identified (success). In turn, if for any test case the obtained output differs from what was expected, then a defect was revealed (failure).

- Example for a program that calculates powers of 2: $(d, S(d)) = (5, 25)$

Testing techniques and criteria

- To guarantee the absence of defects in P it would be necessary to perform an exhaustive test (execute P with all elements of $D(P)$) → the cardinality of $D(P)$ makes this impractical
- Then, the aim is to identify and use a **reduced** subset of $D(P)$, which demands the **minimum time and effort**, but which presents a **high probability of uncovering defects**
- Test subdomains: subsets of $D(P)$ with similar test data (same expected behavior for P)
 - A test set formed by one element from each subdomain would be quite reduced regarding $D(P)$, but in a certain way it would fully represent it

Testing techniques and criteria

- Need to identify test subdomains → **testing criteria** → "rules" to decide whether or not test data should be in the same subdomain
- There are several testing criteria, which are usually grouped into **techniques** that are complementary and differentiated by the source/type of information used to establish the subdomains
- Functional technique:** (1) equivalence partitioning; (2) boundary value analysis; and (3) systematic functional testing
 - Functional technique criteria: are the most commonly used in industry [8, 9] and the most included in academic curricula [7, 10]
 - (1) and (2) are the most used in Brazilian industries [8]
 - (1), (2), and (3) are the most approached in higher education courses (globally) [7]

Functional technique

- The test subdomains are defined based only on the program's **specifications**; details of its implementation/internal structure are not considered for this purpose (the system is considered a **black box**)
- From the specifications, the functions that the software must perform are identified and test cases are created to evaluate these functions
- It mainly aims to reveal defects related to incorrect or missing functions, behavior, performance, and interface errors
- As it is based just on specifications:
 - Advantages:** can be applied to software developed in any programming paradigm and in all testing phases
 - Disadvantages:** depends on a good requirements specification; its criteria cannot guarantee that critical and essential parts of the code are exercised

Equivalence partitioning

- Divides the input domain into **equivalence classes** (elements of a class are treated the same according to the program specification)
- 2 steps:
 - 1st) Identify equivalence classes: each input condition must be analyzed (usually by looking for terms in the specifications that indicate that the data are processed in the same way) and partitioned into two or more groups
 - 2nd) Define test cases

Equivalence partitioning - Step 1 - Guidelines

- If the input condition specifies a **range of values**, one valid and two invalid classes must be defined.

- E.g.:* condition: "the grade given to a student must be between 0,0 and 10,0"

- If the input condition specifies a **number of values** or requires a **specific value**, one valid class and two invalid classes must be defined

- E.g.:* for the condition "the code must be formed by 8 digits" the classes "code with 8 digits" (valid), "code with less than 8 digits" (invalid) and "code with more than 8 digits" (invalid) would be created

Equivalence partitioning - Step 1 - Guidelines

- If the input condition specifies a **specific set of values** and the program can handle them differently, a valid class must be defined for each of the values and an invalid class for another value

- E.g.:* for the condition "a student's final concept can be A, B, C, or F" the valid classes "A", "B", "C", and "F", and an invalid class with a different value (*e.g.:* "X") would be created

- If the input condition is **boolean** (specifying a "must-be" situation), a valid and an invalid class must be defined

- E.g.:* for the condition "the first digit of the registration must be a letter" the classes "first digit is a letter" (valid) and "first digit is not a letter" (invalid) would be created

Equivalence partitioning - Step 2

- To define test cases:

- (2.1) Assign a unique identifier to each equivalence class
- (2.2) As long as there are valid classes not yet covered by test cases, a new test case should be defined (covering as many as possible of the **valid** classes not yet covered)
- (2.3) For each **invalid** class, a test case must be defined, covering it exclusively

- E.g.:* "the grade given to a student must be between 0 and 10"

- (2.1) C1: "0 ≤ grade ≤ 10" (valid), C2: "grade < 0" (invalid), and C3: "grade > 10" (invalid)
- (2.2) C1: (7, input accepted)
- (2.3) C2: (-4, input refused) and C3: (12, input refused)

Equivalence partitioning - Final considerations

- Suitable for applications where input variables can be easily identified and assume specific values

- Strengths:**

- Creation of a reduced test set regarding the input domain
- Definition of test cases based only on specifications

- Weaknesses:**

- A specification may suggest that a group of data is processed the same way, but in practice this may not occur
- Not easily applicable when the input domain is simple but the processing is complex
- It does not provide guidelines for determining test data and identifying combinations between them that enable more efficient class coverage

Boundary value analysis

- Test cases that **explore boundary conditions** (values exactly on or just above or below the equivalence class limits) are more likely to find defects than those that do not evaluate such conditions

- Used in a complementary manner to equivalence partitioning, even presenting similar advantages and disadvantages. Differences:

- 1st) Presents **guidelines for defining test data**: test data should explore the limits of the equivalence classes (are not selected randomly)
- 2nd) In addition to the input domain, the **output domain** must also be considered for deriving test cases

Boundary value analysis - Guidelines

- If an input condition specifies a **range limited by values 'a' and 'b'**, test cases must be created with the values 'a' and 'b', as well as with values immediately above and below them

- E.g.:* for "the grade given to a student must be between 0,0 and 10,0":

- For a **set/quantity of values**, exercise the minimum and maximum values, as well as values immediately above and below them

- E.g.:* for the condition "the file can contain between 1 and 255 records" it would be necessary to test files with 0, 1, 2, 254, **255**, and 256 records

Boundary value analysis - Guidelines

- Use the previous guidelines for **output conditions**
 - E.g.:* system that presents the summaries of the most relevant articles (up to 4) based on a search
 - Attempts to generate invalid outputs are interesting even though it is not always possible to generate results outside the expected output range

- If the input/output is an **ordered set** (*e.g.:* sequential file, linear list, etc.), attention must be paid to the testing of the first and last elements of the set

- If internal **data structures** of the program prescribe limits, the structure should be tested on its limit
 - E.g.:* for a table that can store at most 50 entries, test it with 49, 50, and 51 entries

- For the definition of **other limit conditions**, use intuition

Systematic functional testing

- It combines equivalence partitioning and boundary value analysis (has similar advantages and disadvantages)

- It seeks to minimize the problem of error masking due to coincident defects¹. To do this, it requires that, after partitioning the input and output domains, **at least two test cases from each equivalence class** must be chosen

- Increases the chance of uncovering data-sensitive defects and the likelihood of achieving a better test coverage

¹A program with defects/failures may coincidentally present a correct result when executed with a certain input data. Thus, when using this data, the failure would not be revealed [2]

Systematic functional testing - Guidelines

- **Numeric values:**
 - For the *input domain*, select input values as follows: (a) for discrete values, test each one; and (b) for a range of values, test endpoints and one interior value for each range
 - For the *output domain*, select inputs that generate outputs as follows: (a) for discrete values, generate each one; and (b) for a range of values, generate each endpoint and at least one interior value for each range
- **Real numbers:** their limits must be analyzed, even though the verification may not be exact due to their storage method. To do this, it is necessary to define a margin of error so that, if exceeded, the value can be considered a distinct input. Furthermore, very small real numbers and the value zero must be selected
- **Different types of values** (e.g.: space, which can be interpreted as zero in a numeric field) must be explored in input and output

Systematic functional testing - Guidelines

- **Special cases** (e.g.: zero) must be selected individually, even if they are in the interior of a range of values. If a value is stored in a field with a bit limit, to ensure that it is stored and retrieved correctly, values must be selected within the limits of the binary representation of the data
- **Illegal values:** must be included in the test cases to ensure that the software rejects them. Additionally, one should also try to generate them as outputs (which should not happen)
- **Text/string type data:** different lengths (including the absence of characters) must be explored; their characters must also be validated (some inputs can be only alphabetic, in other cases alphanumeric, have special characters, etc.)
- **Arrays:** its elements must be tested as if they were common variables. Regarding size, arrays must be tested with intermediate, minimum, and maximum sizes

Comparative example of criteria

- E.g.: "the grade given to a student must be between 0,0 and 10,0"

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3. Free and Informed Consent Form (ICF)

This section presents the ICF used in the experiment (the second page of the document will be presented twice, as it differed between executions). For data protection, the researchers' signatures and personal phone numbers were omitted in the images below.

Instrument content:

FREE AND INFORMED CONSENT FORM (ICF)

Research title: ADoTe: Approach to teaching and learning functional testing technique criteria

Proposing institution and place of research: Federal Technological University of Paraná, Curitiba campus (UTFPR-CT)

Program: Postgraduate Program in Applied Computing (PPGCA/UTFPR-CT)

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A) INFORMATION FOR THE PARTICIPANT

1. Research presentation

You are being invited to participate in a scientific research entitled "ADoTe: Approach to teaching and learning functional testing technique criteria". This research is under the responsibility of Maria Claudia Emer, Vladimir Belinski, and Adolfo Gustavo Serra Seca Neto, researchers from the Postgraduate Program in Applied Computing (PPGCA) of the Federal Technological University of Paraná, Curitiba campus (UTFPR-CT).

This document is called Free and Informed Consent Form (ICF). It contains the main information about the research. In order to ensure your rights regarding your participation in the study, it is important and necessary that you keep a copy of this form and the other research questionnaires. Therefore, we advise you to always download or print the document/page from your browser after reading and completing the terms and questionnaires presented to you (for example: using the Ctrl+P shortcut, selecting, if possible, the option to display page numbers/headers and footers).

Context and research rationale: despite the importance of software testing, higher education students (including those who have already graduated) often have knowledge gaps and inadequate habits regarding topics of this subject (such as functional testing technique criteria). This causes problems for students and for the software industry. Thus, the industry demands a better testing education from academy. This research is justified due to this demand/context, and seeks to support and improve software testing education.

ICF second page (1st execution):

2. Research objective

The research objective is to evaluate two approaches to teaching and learning functional testing technique criteria regarding their impact on student motivation and learning.

3. Participation in the research

Your participation in this research is voluntary (without remuneration or rewards) and not mandatory. You are completely free to decide whether you wish to participate, and you will not suffer any type of penalty if you choose not to participate.

The method that will be used in the research is known as a controlled experiment. Thus, students who agree to participate will be randomly divided into two groups (named control group and experimental group) balanced regarding the number of participants and their Academic Performance Coefficient (APC) values. Both groups will fill out questionnaires and participate in a teaching and learning moment about the content "functional testing technique criteria" (specifically equivalence partitioning, boundary value analysis, and systematic functional testing). However, in each group a specific teaching and learning approach will be used.

The experiment will be conducted in the labs of UTFPR-CT, during class periods and on two days: 1st day (today, during the remaining time of this class); and 2nd day (next class; during the entire class). If you agree to collaborate with this research, your participation will consist of doing the following activities (the time that will be allocated to each one is indicated below):

- In this class, you will: fill out an online participant characterization questionnaire (6 closed questions about your age, gender, course, professional experience, and level of knowledge about functional testing technique criteria; 5 min) and an online questionnaire to assess your prior knowledge about the content to be taught (10 multiple-choice questions; 40 min). Then, you will participate in the first moment of the approaches: you will watch a video (with a theoretical focus) about functional testing technique criteria (25 min); after that, you will be allowed to discuss and ask questions about the content of the video to the researchers (20 min).
- In the next class (2nd day): after the division of the participants (by the researchers) into two groups (15 minutes), you will be submitted to the second part of one of the teaching and learning approaches (70 minutes). Each group will be accompanied by a researcher and will solve exercises with a practical focus. In the last 10 minutes of this time, you will be asked to fill out an online retrospective questionnaire (3 open-ended questions for you to report what went well or not regarding the activities of the approach, as well as to suggest improvements). Once this is done, you will answer an online questionnaire about your motivation regarding the approach (giving a score from 1 to 7 for 30 statements; 10 minutes) and an online questionnaire to assess your knowledge about the content taught after being submitted to the approach (10 multiple-choice questions; 40 minutes).

If you choose not to participate in the research (or withdraw from it at any time), you must remain in the laboratory with the other students (on the 1st day) and attend the class as usual (on the 2nd day). On both days, the professor of the course will give you activities about the same content of this research (reading and summary materials, videos, and exercises). These activities must be done in the same environment/laboratory where the professor is and must be handed in during your respective classes. Questions may be clarified verbally with the professor.

ICF second page (2nd execution):

2. Research objective

The research objective is to evaluate two approaches to teaching and learning functional testing technique criteria regarding their impact on student motivation and learning.

3. Participation in the research

Your participation in this research is voluntary (without remuneration or rewards) and not mandatory. You are completely free to decide whether you wish to participate, and you will not suffer any type of penalty if you choose not to participate.

The method that will be used in the research is known as a controlled experiment. Thus, students who agree to participate will be randomly divided into two groups (named control group and experimental group) balanced regarding the number of participants and their Academic Performance Coefficient (APC) values. Both groups will fill out questionnaires and participate in a teaching and learning moment about the content "functional testing technique criteria" (specifically equivalence partitioning, boundary value analysis, and systematic functional testing). However, in each group a specific teaching and learning approach will be used.

The experiment will be conducted in the labs of UTFPR-CT, during class periods and on two days: 1st day (today, during the remaining time of this class); and 2nd day (next class; during the entire class). If you agree to collaborate with this research, your participation will consist of doing the following activities (the time that will be allocated to each one is indicated below):

- In this class, you will: fill out an online participant characterization questionnaire (6 closed questions about your age, gender, course, professional experience, and level of knowledge about functional testing technique criteria; 5 min) and an online questionnaire to assess your prior knowledge about the content to be taught (10 multiple-choice questions; 30 min). Then, you will participate in the first moment of the approaches: you will watch a video (with a theoretical focus) about functional testing technique criteria (25 min); after that, you will be allowed to discuss and ask questions about the content of the video to the researchers (30 min).
- In the next class (2nd day): after the division of the participants (by the researchers) into two groups (10 minutes), you will be submitted to the second part of one of the teaching and learning approaches (110 minutes). Each group will be accompanied by a researcher and will solve exercises with a practical focus. In the last 10 minutes of this time, you will be asked to fill out an online retrospective questionnaire (3 open-ended questions for you to report what went well or not regarding the activities of the approach, as well as to suggest improvements). Once this is done, you will answer an online questionnaire about your motivation regarding the approach (giving a score from 1 to 7 for 30 statements; 10 minutes) and an online questionnaire to assess your knowledge about the content taught after being submitted to the approach (10 multiple-choice questions; 30 minutes).

If you choose not to participate in the research (or withdraw from it at any time), you must remain in the laboratory with the other students (on the 1st day) and attend the class as usual (on the 2nd day). On both days, the professor of the course will give you activities about the same content of this research (reading and summary materials, videos, and exercises). These activities must be done in the same environment/laboratory where the professor is and must be handed in during your respective classes. Questions may be clarified verbally with the professor.

4. Confidentiality

During all phases of this research, your confidentiality, secrecy, and privacy will be guaranteed. Any data that could allow your identification will be omitted when publishing the results. Furthermore, in analyses and publications you will be represented by a code (such as "participant 1") and not by personal data.

The data collected will be used solely for the purpose specified in this research, and will be kept in a safe place, in a physical or digital file, under the custody and responsibility of the researchers for a period of five years after the end of the research.

5. Risks and Benefits

5a. Risks:

During the research, there may be moments when you will need to interact/talk with other participants and researchers (sharing your opinion on what the correct answer to an exercise is, for example), as well as answer online knowledge tests. Possible discomfort/embarrassment regarding these interactions and activities (due to shyness and nervousness, for example) is understood as a risk. To minimize this risk, we emphasize (and will reinforce during the study) that you will be participating in a learning moment, and that it is acceptable and even expected that you make mistakes, since these are part of the learning process. Furthermore, interactions between participants should be collaborative and non-competitive, seeking mutual learning. In turn, knowledge tests aim to assess the approach to which you will be submitted, and there is no need to feel discomfort or embarrassment regarding your own knowledge when answering them. In any case, if necessary, feel free to talk to the researchers, who will provide you with the necessary assistance.

Furthermore, since some stages of the study will be conducted online, this research is subject to risks that are characteristic of the virtual environment and electronic media, such as the risk of data/confidentiality leak. To minimize this risk: (a) we have chosen a secure, widely known, and used tool for data collection, Google Forms. Furthermore, to register your consent, you will be instructed to use secure webmail and electronic signature services. As a limitation, we inform you that the tools/services have security and privacy policies that cannot be controlled by the researchers; and (b) once data collection is complete, the researchers will download the data to a local electronic device, and any data that may characterize the participants will be deleted from virtual platforms, shared environments or the "cloud".

5b. Benefits:

The benefits related to your collaboration in this research are: (a) for you, as a participant: you will receive free explanations/training about software testing, mainly about the functional technique criteria known as equivalence partitioning, boundary value analysis and systematic functional testing; (b) for science: by participating you will be supporting research that will contribute to the role of studies that seek to improve the teaching and learning of software testing; and (c) for society: by contributing to this study you will be able to help train more motivated and qualified professionals to work in the area, as well as collaborate with the provision of higher quality software solutions/products to society.

6. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

6a. Inclusion: to participate in this research you must be a student enrolled in the discipline "Software Engineering 2" offered in the Information Systems course at UTFPR-CT, be legally capable and over 18 years old.

6b. Exclusion: does not apply.

7. Right to receive clarifications during the process, choose to answer questions and leave the research

At any time, during the research or later, you may ask the researchers for clarification about your participation and/or the study, in person or through the contact channels specified in this term.

You are also guaranteed the right not to answer any question, without the need for explanation or justification.

Furthermore, you are completely free to withdraw your consent/withdraw from participating in this study at any time, without any penalty. To do this, send an email to vladimir_belinski@hotmail.com indicating your interest in withdrawing your consent, which will be replied by the researcher responsible for this contact.

However, we would like to highlight that your participation is very important for the research, as well as providing answers to all questions presented.

8. Reimbursement and compensation

You are guaranteed the right to reimbursement in the event of expenses demonstrably related to your participation in the study. You will also be guaranteed, in accordance with the law, the right to assistance and compensation in the event of any damages caused by the research.

9. Disclosure and access to research results

The research results will be published in scientific events and/or venues, including a dissertation to be made available in a public repository of UTFPR. All publications will maintain the confidentiality of the participants' personal data.

Furthermore, participants are guaranteed access to the research results. If you are interested in receiving the results of this research, you can check the following field:

- I want to receive the research results (send to the e-mail: _____)
- I do not want to receive the research results

10. Consent process

To consent to the research (i.e., accept to participate) you must send this form completed and signed to vladimir_belinski@hotmail.com via your email account.

Note 1: to sign the term, we recommend the use of a free and secure electronic signature service. We recommend using the free electronic signature service of the Brazilian Federal Government (<https://www.gov.br/pt-br/servicos/assinatura-eletronica>).

Note 2: we recommend completing this form using a free and secure PDF editing tool/service (such as the one available at <https://www.adobe.com/acrobat/online/sign-pdf.html>).

Once the consent process is complete, you must wait for the researchers' instructions to: (a) begin your participation in the study, if you have consented to the research; or (b) otherwise, do the activities intended for non-study participants (as presented in item "3. Participation in the research"). The researchers will provide you with the instructions verbally after the time agreed in class for reading this form and giving consent.

CLARIFICATIONS ON THE RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

The Research Ethics Committee involving human subjects (CEP) is made up of a team of professionals with multidisciplinary training who are working to ensure that your rights as a research participant are respected. Its purpose is to assess whether the research was planned and whether it will be carried out ethically. If you believe that the research is not being conducted as you were informed or that you are being harmed in any way, please contact the Research Ethics Committee involving human subjects of the Federal Technological University of Paraná (CEP/UTFPR). **Address:** Av. Sete de Setembro, 3165, Block L, Room 07 (central courtyard), Ground Floor, Rebouças, ZIP Code 80230-901, Curitiba-PR. **Phone number:** (41) 3310-4494. **E-mail:** coep@utfpr.edu.br.

B) CONSENT

I declare that, after reading this term, having reflected on it and after a reasonable time to make a decision, I freely and voluntarily accept to participate in this research.

Full name: _____

ID: _____ Birth date ___/___/____ Phone number: _____

Address: _____

ZIP Code: _____ City: _____ State: _____

Signature: _____

Date ___/___/____

As researchers, we declare that we have complied with the requirements contained in items IV. 3 of Resolution 466/2012 and other applicable regulations, having presented the study and its guarantees to the participants, explained the justification, objectives, nature, procedures, risks and benefits of the research, as well as answered the questions posed to us in the best possible way.

Maria Claudia Emer

Vladimir Belinski

Adolfo Gustavo Serra Seca Neto

For all questions regarding the study or to withdraw from it, participants may contact the researchers through the contact channels below (email or phone number/WhatsApp):

Maria Claudia Emer
mcemer@utfpr.edu.br
(xx) xxxx-xxxx

Vladimir Belinski
vladimir_belinski@hotmail.com
(xx) xxxx-xxxx

Adolfo Gustavo Serra Seca Neto
adolfo@utfpr.edu.br
(xx) xxxx-xxxx

Contact of the Research Ethics Committee involving human subjects for reporting, appealing or complaining about research participants: Research Ethics Committee involving human subjects of the Federal Technological University of Paraná (CEP/UTFPR). **Address:** Av. Sete de Setembro, 3165, Block L, Room 07 (central courtyard), Ground Floor, Rebouças, ZIP Code 80230-901, Curitiba-PR. **Phone number:** (41) 3310-4494. **E-mail:** coep@utfpr.edu.br.

4. Participant characterization questionnaire

Instrument content:

Participant Characterization Questionnaire

The following questions aim to characterize your profile as a study participant.

Note: as presented in the ICF, in this research you are guaranteed the right not to answer questions (the reason why none of them have been configured as mandatory in this form). However, even though they are not mandatory, for the research it is very important that you fill in all fields and answer all the questions presented. Furthermore, we advise you to check that you have not left any field/question unanswered by mistake before submitting this form.

Full name:

Information requested since your responses to different questionnaires will need to be analyzed together. However, we remind you that your confidentiality, secrecy and privacy will be maintained throughout the research.

Your answer _____

1. How old are you?

Enter only numbers

Your answer _____

2. What is your gender?

- Female
- Male
- I prefer not to answer
- Other: _____

3. What is your course?

- Computer Science
- Computer Engineering
- Information Systems
- Other: _____

4. What is your course period/phase?

- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
-

5. Indicate your professional experience with activities related to:

	None	Up to 2 years	From 2 to 4 years	From 4 to 6 years	More than 6 years
Requirements elicitation and/or specification	<input type="radio"/>				
Software architecture	<input type="radio"/>				
Coding/development	<input type="radio"/>				
Software testing	<input type="radio"/>				
Data analysis and/or management	<input type="radio"/>				

Support activities	<input type="radio"/>				
IT infrastructure (e.g.: networks, application servers)	<input type="radio"/>				
Software project management	<input type="radio"/>				
Team management/leadership	<input type="radio"/>				

6. What is your level of knowledge about functional technique testing criteria (equivalence partitioning, boundary value analysis and systematic functional testing)?

- None: I don't know the subject
- Theoretical (only): I know the theoretical concepts of one or more of these criteria, but I have never applied them in practice
- Practical (academic application only): in my academic training I have already applied one or more of these criteria in a practical way, but never professionally
- Practical (industrial application): in my professional activity I have already applied one or more of these criteria in a practical way
- I prefer not to answer

Submit

Clear form

Participant Characterization Questionnaire

Your answers have been recorded.

Please wait for further instructions from the researchers. These will be announced verbally to all participants after the agreed time for completing this questionnaire has ended.

5. Retrospective questionnaire

Instrument content:

Retrospective Questionnaire

In this questionnaire we seek to collect your perceptions about the teaching and learning approach, as well as suggestions for improvement.

Therefore, the following questions must be answered considering the teaching and learning activity in which you participated (video with theoretical concepts followed by a practical moment/exercises).

Full name:

Information requested since your responses to different questionnaires will need to be analyzed together. However, we remind you that your confidentiality, secrecy and privacy will be maintained throughout the research.

Your answer _____

1. What went well in the activity? What helped your learning?

Your answer _____

2. What didn't go so well in the activity? What hindered your learning?

Your answer _____

3. Do you have any suggestions for improving the activity? If so, what are your suggestions?

Your answer _____

Submit

Clear form

6. Intrinsic Motivation Inventory (IMI)

Scoring information (for researchers use; the letter R indicates an item with reverse meaning): interest/enjoyment: 1, 6, 10 (R), 14, 19, 23, 30 (R); perceived competence: 3 (R), 7, 11, 16, 22, 28; pressure/tension: 5, 13, 18 (R), 24 (R), 27; effort/importance: 2, 9 (R), 21, 26 (R), 29; value/usefulness: 4, 8, 12, 15, 17, 20, 25.

Instrument content:

Intrinsic Motivation Inventory (IMI)

The following statements are intended to assess your motivation regarding the teaching and learning approach.

Note: in this survey, you are guaranteed the right not to answer questions (the reason why none of them have been configured as mandatory in this form). However, even though they are not mandatory, for the research it is very important that you fill in all fields and select an answer for each of the thirty statements presented. Furthermore, we advise you to check that you have not left any field/statement unanswered by mistake before submitting this form.

Full name:

Information requested since your responses to different questionnaires will need to be analyzed together. However, we remind you that your confidentiality, secrecy and privacy will be maintained throughout the research.

Your answer

Considering the teaching and learning activity in which you participated (video with theoretical concepts followed by a practical moment/exercises), for each sentence below indicate how true it is for you using the following numerical scale:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7
not true a little bit true true

After working at this activity for awhile, I felt pretty competent

While I was doing this activity, I was thinking about how much I enjoyed it

I did not feel nervous at all while doing this

I think this is important to do because it can help in the teaching and learning of functional testing technique criteria

I didn't put much energy into this

I felt pressured while doing these

I think I am pretty good at this activity

I tried very hard on this activity

I thought this was a boring activity

Submit

Clear form

7. Knowledge pre-test

Correct answers: 1-B, 2-A, 3-A, 4-C, 5-E, 6-E, 7-D, 8-B, 9-C, 10-D

Instrument content:

Knowledge pre-test

The following questions are intended to assess your knowledge regarding topics related to software testing **before** you participate in the teaching and learning activity. Therefore, it is important that you follow the recommendations below:

- To answer the questions, consider just your current knowledge (do not consult materials, colleagues, etc.); and
- Try to answer as many questions correctly as possible. However, if you don't know an answer, mark "I don't know" instead of choosing a random answer/simple "guessing".

Note: as presented in the ICF, in this research you are guaranteed the right not to answer questions (the reason why none of them have been configured as mandatory in this form). However, even though they are not mandatory, for the research it is very important that you fill in all fields and answer all the questions presented. Furthermore, we advise you to check that you have not left any field/question unanswered by mistake before submitting this form.

Full name:

Information requested since your responses to different questionnaires will need to be analyzed together. However, we remind you that your confidentiality, secrecy and privacy will be maintained throughout the research.

Your answer _____

1. Regarding software testing, consider the following statements:

- I. Testing involves executing a program or model with some particular input data and checking its behavior (whether it matches what is expected)
- II. It is possible to prove the absence of faults/defects through testing, since exhaustive testing is usually possible
- III. One of the objectives of testing is to reveal the presence of faults/defects if they exist
- IV. A good test suite should require minimal time and effort for the testing activity, but have a high probability of uncovering faults/defects
- V. A test case consists of a test data and the result obtained from executing the software with this test data

Select the CORRECT alternative:

- (A) Only statements III and V are true
- (B) Only statements I, III, and IV are true
- (C) Only statements I, II, III, and IV are true
- (D) Only statement V is true
- (E) All statements are true
- I don't know

2. Regarding the functional software testing technique, select the INCORRECT alternative:

- (A) Considers details of the implementation/internal structure of the program to derive test cases
- (B) It seeks to uncover faults/defects related to, for example, incorrect or missing functions
- (C) It can be applied in all testing phases and for software developed in any programming paradigm
- (D) A disadvantage of the criteria of this technique is the dependence on a good requirements specification
- (E) It is also often called black box
- I don't know

3. Match the testing criteria to their definitions/characteristics:

Testing criteria:

- I. Systematic functional testing
- II. Equivalence partitioning
- III. Boundary value analysis

Definitions/characteristics:

- a. Divides the input domain into groups in which any element can be taken as a representative for executing the test
- b. Selects values that are exactly on or immediately above or below the edges of semantically equivalent classes
- c. Among the criteria listed, this is the one that usually results in larger test sets

The CORRECT sequence of associations is:

- (A) I-c, II-a, III-b
- (B) I-b, II-c, III-a
- (C) I-a, II-b, III-c
- (D) I-b, II-a, III-c
- (E) I-a, II-c, III-b
- I don't know

4. A computed tomography system allows the configuration of the tomography device through a numeric keypad. One of the requirements of this system is: only values between 1.5 mSv and 6.0 mSv (millisievert) should be accepted in the field related to radiation dose. Considering the equivalence partitioning criterion, what is the minimum number of test cases required to test all equivalence classes related to the presented requirement?

- (A) 1
- (B) 2
- (C) 3
- (D) 4
- (E) 5
- I don't know

5. One of the requirements of a file manager for a given operating system is: file names cannot contain any of the following characters: \ / : * ? " < > |. Which of the alternatives below presents (at a high level) the test data needed to test this requirement in the most appropriate way according to the equivalence partitioning criterion?

- (A) 1 test data: name that uses at the same time \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, and |
- (B) 2 test data: (1st) name that does not use \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, or |; (2nd) name that uses at the same time \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, and |
- (C) 2 test data: (1st) name that does not use \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, or |; (2nd) name that uses one or more of the characters \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, and |
- (D) 8 test data: (1st) name that does not use \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, or |; (2nd) name with \ or /; (3rd) name with < or >; (4th to 8th) 5 names, each one presenting only one of the following characters (i.e., testing them exclusively): *, :, ", and |
- (E) 10 test data: (1st) name that does not use \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, or |; (2nd to 10th) 9 names, each one presenting only one of the following characters (i.e., testing them exclusively): \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, and |
- I don't know

6. A music player has a feature that allows selecting the playback speed through a drop-down list field. The available speed options are 0.25x, 0.5x, 0.75x, 1x, 1.25x, 1.5x, 1.75x, and 2x. Select the option that presents the test data required to test this feature considering the equivalence partitioning criterion:

- (A) A test with just one of the options (whatever the option) is sufficient
- (B) 0.25x and 2x
- (C) 0.25x, 1x, 1.25x, and 2x
- (D) 0.5x, 1x, 1.5x, and 2x
- (E) 0.25x, 0.5x, 0.75x, 1x, 1.25x, 1.5x, 1.75x, and 2x
- I don't know

7. The Brazilian National Treasury is implementing an API for issuing a financial document. One of the requirements related to the validation of the data that will be received through this API is: the value of "management_unit" must be composed of six digits. Considering this requirement, which alternative below presents test data ("management_unit" values) that best meet the guidelines of

the Equivalence Class Partitioning (ECP) and Boundary Value Analysis (BVA) criteria?

Note: evaluate each data set (enclosed in { }) only regarding the criterion to which it is associated (given before the = character). Test data is separated by the comma character.

- (A) ECP = {12345, 123456, 1234567} | BVA = {12, 123456, 123456789}
- (B) ECP = {1234, 12345, 123456} | BVA = {1, 12345, 1234567}
- (C) ECP = {123, 1234567, 12345678} | BVA = {12345, 123456, 1234567}
- (D) ECP = {12, 123456, 123456789} | BVA = {12345, 123456, 1234567}
- (E) ECP = {123456, 1234567, 123456789} | BVA = {1, 12345, 1234567}
- I don't know

8. A function used in an aircraft control system receives as a parameter a real number with precision of one decimal place. This function behaves correctly only if the number informed as the parameter is contained in a specific range. Knowing this, one of the requirements associated with this function is: the number informed as the parameter must only be accepted if it is between -2.0 and 2.0 (including these values). Which alternative below presents the minimum set of test data necessary to test this requirement considering the boundary value analysis criterion?

- (A) -2.0, -1.9, 0.0, 1.9, and 2.0
- (B) -2.1, -2.0, -1.9, 1.9, 2.0, and 2.1
- (C) -2.1, -2.0, -1.9, 0.0, 1.9, 2.0, and 2.1
- (D) -3.0, -2.0, -1.0, 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0
- (E) -3.0, -2.0, -1.0, 0.0, 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0
- I don't know

9. Among the test data sets presented below, which is the best for testing the requirement of question 8 considering the guidelines of the systematic functional testing criterion?

- (A) -2.0, -1.9, -0.5, 0.0, 0.5, 1.9, and 2.0
- (B) -4.0, -2.1, -2.0, -1.9, 1.9, 2.0, and 2.1
- (C) -4.0, -2.1, -2.0, -1.9, 0.0, 1.9, 2.0, 2.1, and 4.0

- (D) -4.0, -3.0, -2.0, -1.0, 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0
- (E) -4.0, -3.0, -2.0, -1.0, 0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, and 4.0
- I don't know

10. Regarding the systematic functional testing criterion and its guidelines, consider the following statements:

- I. It suggests that, in addition to the input domain, the output domain should also be considered for deriving test cases
- II. It suggests testing different types of values (e.g.: white space, which can be interpreted as zero in a numeric field)
- III. It suggests that strings should be tested for varying lengths (including length 0) and regarding the validity of their characters
- IV. It suggests the testing of arrays/vectors with intermediate, minimum and maximum sizes

Select the CORRECT alternative:

- (A) Only statement II is true
- (B) Only statements III and IV are true
- (C) Only statement I is false
- (D) All statements are true
- (E) All statements are false
- I don't know

Submit

Clear form

Knowledge pre-test

Your answers have been recorded.

Please wait for further instructions from the researchers. These will be announced verbally to all participants after the agreed time for completing this questionnaire has ended.

8. Knowledge post-test

Correct answers: 1-C, 2-D, 3-B, 4-C, 5-A, 6-D, 7-A, 8-E, 9-D, 10-B

Instrument content:

Knowledge post-test

The following questions are intended to assess your knowledge regarding topics related to software testing **after** your participation in the teaching and learning activity. Therefore, it is important that you follow the recommendations below:

- To answer the questions, consider the concepts that were presented to you and your current knowledge (do not consult materials, colleagues, etc.). This is important so that we can properly analyze the teaching approach in which you participated; and
- Try to answer as many questions correctly as possible. However, if you don't know an answer, mark "I don't know" instead of choosing a random answer/simply "guessing".

Note: as presented in the ICF, in this research you are guaranteed the right not to answer questions (the reason why none of them have been configured as mandatory in this form). However, even though they are not mandatory, for the research it is very important that you fill in all fields and answer all the questions presented. Furthermore, we advise you to check that you have not left any field/question unanswered by mistake before submitting this form.

Full name:

Information requested since your responses to different questionnaires will need to be analyzed together. However, we remind you that your confidentiality, secrecy and privacy will be maintained throughout the research.

Your answer _____

1. Regarding software testing, consider the following statements:

I. Testing involves executing a program or model with some particular input data and checking its behavior (whether it matches what is expected)

II. One of the objectives of testing is to reveal the presence of faults/defects if they exist

III. It is possible to prove the absence of faults/defects through testing, since exhaustive testing is usually possible

IV. A test case consists of a test data and the result obtained from executing the software with this test data

V. A good test suite should require minimal time and effort for the testing activity, but have a high probability of uncovering faults/defects

Select the CORRECT alternative:

- (A) Only statement IV is true
- (B) Only statements II and IV are true
- (C) Only statements I, II, and V are true
- (D) Only statements I, II, III, and V are true
- (E) All statements are true
- I don't know

2. Regarding the functional software testing technique, select the INCORRECT alternative:

- (A) It is also often called black box
- (B) It seeks to uncover faults/defects related to, for example, incorrect or missing functions
- (C) It can be applied in all testing phases and for software developed in any programming paradigm
- (D) Considers details of the implementation/internal structure of the program to derive test cases
- (E) A disadvantage of the criteria of this technique is the dependence on a good requirements specification
- I don't know

3. Match the testing criteria to their definitions/characteristics:

Testing criteria:

- I. Boundary value analysis
- II. Systematic functional testing
- III. Equivalence partitioning

Definitions/characteristics:

- a. Divides the input domain into groups in which any element can be taken as a representative for executing the test
- b. Selects values that are exactly on or immediately above or below the edges of semantically equivalent classes
- c. Among the criteria listed, this is the one that usually results in larger test sets

The CORRECT sequence of associations is:

- (A) I-c, II-a, III-b
- (B) I-b, II-c, III-a
- (C) I-a, II-b, III-c
- (D) I-b, II-a, III-c
- (E) I-a, II-c, III-b
- I don't know

4. A hemodialysis machine allows the healthcare professional to set some parameters using a numeric keypad before starting each procedure. One of the requirements of the system in this machine is: only values between 130.0 mmol/l and 145.0 mmol/l should be accepted as the sodium concentration to be used in the dialysate. Considering the equivalence partitioning criterion, what is the minimum number of test cases required to test all equivalence classes related to the presented requirement?

- (A) 5
- (B) 4
- (C) 3
- (D) 2
- (E) 1
- I don't know

5. One of the requirements of a file manager for a given operating system is: file names cannot contain any of the following characters: \ / : * ? " < > |. Which of the alternatives below presents (at a high level) the test data needed to test this requirement in the most appropriate way according to the equivalence partitioning criterion?

- (A) 10 test data: (1st) name that does not use \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, or |; (2nd to 10th) 9 names, each one presenting only one of the following characters (i.e., testing them exclusively): \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, and |
- (B) 8 test data: (1st) name that does not use \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, or |; (2nd) name with \ or /; (3rd) name with < or >; (4th to 8th) 5 names, each one presenting only one of the following characters (i.e., testing them exclusively): *, :, ?, ", and |
- (C) 2 test data: (1st) name that does not use \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, or |; (2nd) name that uses at the same time \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, and |
- (D) 2 test data: (1st) name that does not use \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, or |; (2nd) name that uses one or more of the characters \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, and |
- (E) 1 test data: name that uses at the same time \, /, :, *, ?, ", <, >, and |
- I don't know

6. A video player has a feature that allows selecting the resolution through a drop-down list field. The available resolution options are 1080p, 720p, 480p, 360p, 240p, and 144p. Select the option that presents the test data required to test this feature considering the equivalence partitioning criterion:

- (A) 1080p and 144p
- (B) 720p, 360p, and 144p
- (C) 1080p, 480p, 360p, and 144p
- (D) 1080p, 720p, 480p, 360p, 240p, and 144p
- (E) A test with just one of the options (whatever the option) is sufficient
- I don't know

7. Recently, a team from the Brazilian Superior Electoral Court refactored the system used in electronic voting machines. One of the refactored functions concerns the validation of candidate numbers, and one of the requirements associated with this functionality is the following: for the position of federal deputy, only numbers consisting of four digits should be accepted. Considering

this requirement, which alternative below presents test data (candidate numbers) that best meets the guidelines of the Equivalence Class Partitioning (ECP) and Boundary Value Analysis (BVA) criteria?

Note: evaluate each data set (enclosed in { }) only regarding the criterion to which it is associated (given before the = character). Test data is separated by the comma character.

- (A) ECP = {12, 1234, 1234567} | BVA = {123, 1234, 12345}
- (B) ECP = {123, 1234, 12345} | BVA = {12, 1234, 1234567}
- (C) ECP = {12, 123, 1234} | BVA = {1, 123, 12345}
- (D) ECP = {12, 12345, 123456} | BVA = {123, 1234, 12345}
- (E) ECP = {1234, 12345, 1234567} | BVA = {1, 123, 12345}
- I don't know

8. A function used in a rocket launch control system receives as a parameter a real number with precision of one decimal place. This function behaves correctly only if the number informed as the parameter is contained in a specific range. Knowing this, one of the requirements associated with this function is: the number informed as the parameter must only be accepted if it is between -5.0 and 5.0 (including these values). Which alternative below presents the minimum set of test data necessary to test this requirement considering the boundary value analysis criterion?

- (A) -5.0, -4.9, 0.0, 4.9, and 5.0
- (B) -6.0, -5.0, -4.0, 0.0, 4.0, 5.0, and 6.0
- (C) -6.0, -5.0, -4.0, 4.0, 5.0, and 6.0
- (D) -5.1, -5.0, -4.9, 0.0, 4.9, 5.0, and 5.1
- (E) -5.1, -5.0, -4.9, 4.9, 5.0, and 5.1
- I don't know

9. Among the test data sets presented below, which is the best for testing the requirement of question 8 considering the guidelines of the systematic functional testing criterion?

- (A) -5.0, -4.9, -2.0, 0.0, 2.0, 4.9, and 5.0
- (B) -10.0, -6.0, -5.0, -4.0, 0.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, and 10.0

- (C) -10.0, -6.0, -5.0, -4.0, 4.0, 5.0, and 6.0
- (D) -10.0, -5.1, -5.0, -4.9, 0.0, 4.9, 5.0, 5.1, and 10.0
- (E) -10.0, -5.1, -5.0, -4.9, 4.9, 5.0, and 5.1
- I don't know

10. Regarding the systematic functional testing criterion and its guidelines, consider the following statements:

I. It suggests that, in addition to the input domain, the output domain should also be considered for deriving test cases

II. It suggests testing different types of values (e.g.: white space, which can be interpreted as zero in a numeric field)

III. It suggests that strings should be tested for varying lengths (including length 0) and regarding the validity of their characters

IV. It suggests the testing of arrays/vectors with intermediate, minimum and maximum sizes

Select the CORRECT alternative:

- (A) All statements are false
- (B) All statements are true
- (C) Only statement II is true
- (D) Only statements III and IV are true
- (E) Only statement I is false
- I don't know

Submit

Clear form

Knowledge post-test

Your answers have been recorded.

Your participation in the survey has ended. We greatly appreciate your collaboration!